

The Dawn of Artificial Intelligence: From Ancient Dreams to Mathematical Foundations

The idea of artificial intelligence was born from questioning first principles — the wisdom of deciding that thought must occur in the brain, computation must take place on discrete, logically organised representations of things, and human intelligence must employ a deductive process. So let's take a trip around castle to see what went on that shaped one of humanity's greatest achievements.

The Seeds of Mechanical Reasoning (Ancient Times - 1900)

Ancient Aspirations

Human desire to replicate artificial life seems across civilizations. But the ancient Egyptians used hidden mechanical devices to animate statues of their gods (Faraone 1992); Greek mythology tells of Daedalus's making the moving statues. These were not mere entertainment — they represented humanity's first attempts to understand and replicate intelligent behavior.

Medieval Developments

Ramon Llull's (in 13th century Spain) mechanical reasoning system constituted a revolution. His "Ars Magna" used rotating wheels with logical propositions, creating what we might today call a "logical computation engine" (Gardner, 1958). Perhaps it was the first attempt to mechanise human thought processes.

The Mathematical Revolution (1800 - 1930)

Boolean Logic: The Language of Thought

George Boole's revolutionary work "An Investigation of the Laws of Thought" (1854) proposed that human reasoning could be reduced to algebraic operations. Consider this groundbreaking idea: Boole suggested that we could tear down human thinking to its basic logical parts as we can solve complex mathematical equations by a set of simple formulae.

Example: The statement "If it is raining (A) and I do not have an umbrella (B), then I will get wet (C)" can be expressed as a logical formula: $(A \text{ AND NOT } B) \rightarrow C$.

Frege's Contribution

Gottlob Frege's "Begriffsschrift" (1879) introduced predicate logic, providing a formal system for expressing complex logical relationships. We were creating a universal grammar for reasoning itself (van Heijenoort, 1967).

The Turing Revolution (1930 - 1950)

The Universal Machine

Turing's concept of computability (1936) was revolutionary. What if we could have a machine that can read, write, and do simple things like follow a recipe like a cook does? Turing proved that such a simple machine could perform any mathematical computation possible. This "Universal Turing Machine" concept demonstrated that complex thinking might be reduced to simple, mechanical steps.

To understand this better, consider a modern smartphone: it is complex, but that is basically doing a simple add, subtract, or compare billions of times per second.

The Imitation Game and Machine Intelligence

Turing's famous 1950 paper "Computing Machinery and Intelligence" proposed what we now call the Turing Test. Rather than asking "Can machines think?", Turing suggested a practical test: if a machine can fool humans into thinking it is human through conversation, is not that a form of intelligence?

Shannon's Information Revolution

Information Theory

As Claude Shannon did in his work (1948), information itself was quantified. The best analogy to think about information could be water being in pipes and flowing; Shannon explained how this flow and exactly the problems areas to look at could be identified were. His binary digit (bit) allowed a measure of information regardless of its content.

Example: Whenever you decide to text your friend, the letters are separated into the bits (1s and 0s), transmitted, and your friend's phone decodes them – all by the principles of Shannon.

The Great Debate: Can Machines Think?

The Mechanist Perspective

The brain was essentially a biological computer, which made proponents say. McCulloch and Pitts (1943) proffered the first convincing demonstration that neural networks could perform logical operations and thereby suggested that thinking may be computational.

Supporters pointed to:

- Overcoming intellectual scepticism in mathematical logic
- A neural brain structure akin to computational networks
- The power to divide large problems in simple operations.

The Anti-Mechanist Arguments

Critics raised substantial objections:

1. Consciousness and Qualia: Thomas Nagel (1974) among philosophers argued that computations would only yield objective experience; this could not resolve its subjective counterpart.
2. Gödel's Incompleteness: Humans understand more than mechanical computation, showed mathematician Kurt Gödel, since any formal system includes truths that it cannot prove (Nagel & Newman, 1958).
3. The Chinese Room: Philosopher John Searle (1980) argued that even if a machine could simulate understanding, it would not truly understand, just as following Chinese conversation rules does not mean understanding Chinese.

Conclusion

The roots of AI can be traced from ageless aspirations, mathematical formalism and information sciences. Just as relativity theory that Einstein brought to impacting system rebelled Newtonian mechanics, these icons shifted conventional knowledge of intelligence and computing.

Their work suggests that intelligence — or at least some aspects of it — may actually be more like a spectrum built around a binary human versus machine divide. The debate continues: or can we actually replicate human thought, or are we actually creating something completely new but equally valuable?

Boldly go where no human or AI has gone before!
Ferhat Sarikaya

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